

**SAĞLIK TURİZMİNİN GELİŞMESİNDE SAĞLIK TURİZMİ SEYAHAT
ACENTELERİNİN ROLÜ VE ÖNEMİ**

**THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF HEALTH TOURISM TRAVEL AGENCIES IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF HEALTH TOURISM**

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ABSTRACT

Health tourism has become a rapidly growing and evolving sector worldwide, gaining significant prominence. The swift developments in this field attract the attention of both countries providing healthcare services and patients seeking treatment. Health tourism is a specialized type of tourism for individuals who travel with the intention of receiving medical treatment outside their place of residence. The aim of this study is to reveal the role and importance of health tourism travel agencies in the development of health tourism. A mixed-methods approach based on both quantitative and qualitative data was employed in the research. The qualitative dimension consisted of a literature review, while the quantitative data were collected through a questionnaire. The sample of the study comprised five agencies selected through purposive sampling. The study was conducted with a total of 25 participants working in these agencies, chosen according to the maximum variation criterion. For the qualitative data collection, relevant studies from the literature were examined. The literature review was carried out on April 15, 2025, using the keywords “health tourism” and “agency” in the abstract search of the YÖK Thesis database. Content analysis and frequency analysis methods were used in the data analysis. The findings indicate that travel agencies generally contribute positively to customer satisfaction. Additionally, factors such as the adoption of the internet, content analysis of websites, and possession of health tourism authorization certificates provide a significant framework for understanding their impact on the development of health tourism. At this point, it is emphasized that health tourism travel agencies need to use information and communication technologies more effectively in order to offer better services and enhance their competitive advantage in the sector.

Keywords: Health Tourism, Travel Agencies, Role, Türkiye.

ÖZET

Sağlık turizmi, dünya genelinde hızla büyüyen ve evrilen bir sektör olarak önemli bir yer edinmiştir. Bu alandaki hızlı gelişmeler, hem sağlık hizmeti sunan ülkelerin hem de hastaların dikkatini çekmektedir. Sağlık turizmi, tedavi amacıyla seyahat edip yerleşim yerlerinin dışında sağlık hizmeti almayı amaçlayan insanlar için özel bir turizm türüdür. Bu çalışmanın amacı sağlık turizminin gelişmesinde sağlık turizmi seyahat acentelerinin rolünün ve öneminin ortaya koymaktır. Araştırmada model olarak hem nicel hem de nitel verilere dayanan karma yöntem işe koşulmuştur. Araştırmanın nitel boyutu ilgili literatür taraması, nicel boyutu ise anket yardımıyla toplanan verilerden oluşmuştur. Araştırmanın örneklemini ise amaçlı örnekleme yoluyla belirlenen 5 acentedir. Toplamda acentede çalışan 25 katılımcı ile çalışma yürütülmüştür. Maximum çeşitlilik kriterine göre tercih edilmişlerdir. Nitel verilerin toplanmasında ise alanyazında bulunan konu ile ilgili araştırmalar incelenecektir.

İlgili tarama 15.04.2025 tarihinde YÖK tez den yapılan anahtar kelimelere “sağlık turizmi” ve “acente” kelimeleri özetle taratılmıştır. Verilerin analizinde içerik analizi ve frekans analiz yöntemleri kullanılmıştır. Bulgular, seyahat acentelerinin genellikle olumlu bir müşteri memnuniyetine katkı sağladığını göstermektedir. Ayrıca, internetin benimsenmesi, web sitelerinin içerik analizi ve sağlık turizmi yetki belgeleri gibi faktörlerin sağlık turizminin gelişimine olan etkilerini anlamak için önemli bir çerçeve sunmaktadır. Bu noktada, sağlık turizmi seyahat acentelerinin daha etkili hizmet sunabilmek ve sektördeki rekabet avantajını artırmak için bilgi iletişim teknolojilerini daha etkin bir şekilde kullanmaları gerektiği öne çıkmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sağlık Turizmi, Seyahat Acenteleri, Rol, Türkiye.

1. INTRODUCTION

Health tourism has gained an important place as a rapidly growing and evolving sector around the world. Rapid developments in this field attract the attention of both healthcare countries and patients. Health tourism is a special type of tourism for people who travel for treatment purposes and aim to receive health services outside of their settlements. Health tourism usually includes individuals with health problems and people who are sensitive about protecting their health. This type of tourism is associated with trips with the aim of seeking a healthier environment, exploring alternative treatment methods or visiting healing natural resources. Health tourism in general; It can be classified as thermal, beauty/wellness or medical tourism (Özçelik, Gül and Kızılırmak, 2021).

Health tourism travel agencies are important intermediaries who guide patient candidates about health services, make travel arrangements and help with destination selection. These agencies provide a variety of services to organize the treatment process of patients, meet logistical requirements such as accommodation and transportation, coordinate with local health institutions, and increase patient satisfaction as part of health tourism. At this point, more research is needed on the role and importance of health tourism travel agencies in the development of health tourism. The effects of these agencies on the destination selection, travel arrangements, and treatment processes of patient candidates should be considered as a critical factor in the growth and sustainability of health tourism (Kaygısız, 2021). However, in the available literature, there is a limited understanding of the role and contributions of health tourism travel agencies in these processes. The aim of this study is to reveal the role and importance of health tourism travel agencies in the development of health tourism.

1.1. Travel Agencies in Health Tourism

Health tourism travel agencies, which enable domestic and foreign patients to be transported from one place to another for treatment purposes; It is defined as organizations that organize the treatment processes of patients from address to address and are responsible for the execution of both travel and medical procedures. In order for a business to be accepted as a health tourism agency, this field of activity must be clearly stated in its articles of association. In addition, in order to benefit from incentives, it is necessary to have a formal agreement with a healthcare institution regarding patient care (Berksoy, Bostan and Dilek, 2023). Travel agencies, which operate for commercial purposes, act as intermediaries in order to provide touristic needs and relocations (Hacıoğlu, 2000: 40). They market the products of tour operators and act as an agency by taking reservations from tour operators, as well as providing local transportation for holiday buyers (Radburn and Goodall, 1991: 237) and play an active role in making holiday decisions by informing consumers about holiday options.

The main function of travel agencies is retailing and distribution of tourist products; however, in some cases, they also take on the role of package tour preparers (Peters, 1969: 228).

Travel agencies are likely to revolve around two main activities, especially the sale of incentive tours and the sale of airline tickets (Radburn and Goodall, 1991: 238). Travel agencies in Turkey are defined according to the Travel Agencies and Travel Agencies Association Law No. 1618 and are commercial organizations that have the authority to provide touristic information, create package tours and market tourism-related services. Medical tourism has become an increasingly fast-growing industry and has become an important source of economic income for many countries. In this context, the contribution and role of health tourism travel agencies to the sector is of critical importance for both health tourists and destination countries. These agencies facilitate interaction by creating an intermediary structure between the institutions providing health services and the individuals requesting the service. In the tourism sector, travel agencies undertake a comprehensive function with services such as experience sharing, package tour organization, transportation and accommodation reservations and car rental and make significant contributions to the execution of tourism activities (Lam and Zhang, 1999).

Travel agencies are divided into three groups: A, B and C. While group A agencies provide all services, group B agencies sell tickets for tours organized by group A agencies with international transportation vehicles. Group C agencies, on the other hand, organize tours only for Turkish citizens. While most of the travel agencies in Turkey are group A agencies, most of the travel agencies are concentrated in important tourism destinations such as Istanbul, Antalya and Muğla. Travel agencies can operate in different branches of tourism that require expertise, such as tourism organizations, outward and outward tours. The majority of agencies in Turkey consist of A groups, and these agencies are generally located in the provinces of Istanbul, Antalya and Muğla. High commission rates and low risk factors encourage Turkish travel agencies to offer the services of package tours organized by foreign tour operators for Turkey.

1.2. Travel Agencies and Information Communication Technologies

Innovation and information technologies stand out as a critical factor in determining competitiveness and performance between nations and companies today (Asongu, Rahman, Nnanna, and Haffar 2020: 2). Technology, which is an important element of globalization, has become a remarkable issue today. The advancement of technology has brought humanity from a small village to a point where it can reach or know about any part of the world. Information technologies is a term that describes technologies that record and store data, produce new information and provide effective access to this information (Tuncay, 2005: 128).

Information technologies, especially since the 90s, when combined with internet technologies, have made great progress in the communication network and the use of the internet has increased rapidly (Taş, Akkaşoğlu and Akyol, 2018: 209). The Internet has become a phenomenon whose main purpose is to provide communication and is routinely used by billions of people (Karamustafa and Öz, 2008: 274). The widespread use of information technologies and the internet has also affected advertising activities and allowed advertisements to spread around the world.

When advertising is integrated with information technologies, it has gained a global dimension, and advertisements have reached all over the world through the internet. The Internet has allowed companies to reach audiences around the world. The tourism sector has been one of the sectors positively affected by advertising, especially thanks to the internet and information technologies. Tourism is a sector where promotion and marketing are intense, and

thanks to the internet and information technologies, it has had the opportunity to reach potential customers more effectively.

Innovations in computers, telephones and other technological tools have changed the methods of advertising (Çakır, 2004: 168). While advances in telecommunication technologies have created a global audience, changes in transportation have created a global village (Nişancı and Özmutaf, 2016: 363).

The rapid development of the internet and information technology industry in recent years has directly or indirectly affected all businesses (Karataş and Babür, 2013: 16). With the emergence of digital hardware (smartphones, tablets, computers), businesses have moved their activities to digital environments and have chosen to maintain their existence in these new environments (Buluk and Boz, 2016: 496). Tourism agencies are experiencing an increasing demand for functionality due to the effective use of websites that they can easily access from anywhere with internet.

1.3. Health Tourism Authorization Certificate

The increasing demand for health tourism around the world has brought with it the need for travel agencies operating in this field. In Turkey, the Ministry of Health published on 13.07.2017 “Regulation on International Health Tourism and Tourist's Health” stipulates that health tourism agencies must fulfill certain conditions. According to the regulation, it is stated that the basic condition for becoming an international health tourism agency is “to be a group A travel agency (agencies that can perform all travel agency services)” and in addition, the following criteria are listed (Official Gazette, 2017).

1. Signing a protocol with at least three health facilities that have an international health tourism authorization certificate.
2. To have an infrastructure that can serve 24 hours a day, 7 days a week in at least two languages (one of the foreign languages must be English).
3. To employ at least two more personnel who speak foreign languages in addition to the personnel who will answer the calls.
4. To comply with certain criteria for foreign language proficiency, for example, to have a minimum score of 65 in the foreign language exams held by OSYM in English or the language of the international health tourist to be served.
5. The agency must commit to meeting certain commitments, for example, having a website that supports at least 3 languages, with Turkish and English being mandatory.

In addition, international health tourism agencies are obliged to fulfill other conditions determined by the Ministry of Health. Agencies that meet these conditions are announced on the website of the Ministry of Health, General Directorate of Health Services, Department of Health Tourism (Ministry of Health, 2021).

There are various studies in the literature on the role of travel agencies and intermediary institutions in the development of health tourism. Kalbaska (2011) examined the online training programs offered by destination management organizations in order to ensure that travel agencies are better equipped in destination promotion and sales. It has been determined that these B2B-oriented programs provide strategic content on destination information and marketing of touristic services and provide competitive advantage for travel agencies in the digital environment. Discussing the transformation in the tourism sector, Jansen van Rensburg (2014) emphasized that information and communication technologies play an important role in the development of customer-centered marketing strategies by

integrating with traditional agency services. This study reveals that classic agency services are still relevant and add value to customers.

Focusing on the marketing techniques used by travel agencies, Bunghez (2020) stated that grouped sales, early booking and last-minute campaigns are common; He stated that transportation and accommodation services are decisive in consumer decisions. One of the important findings of the study is that free additional services increase customer loyalty. Looking at the specific research on health tourism, Mohamad et al. (2012) found that medical travel agencies play a facilitating role in many areas such as the selection of health institutions, transportation organization and planning of touristic activities in international patient mobility. This makes these agencies effective actors in the sector.

In the studies conducted specifically for Turkey, Daştan (2014) analyzed the current situation of health tourism, based in Izmir, and presented strategic suggestions with SWOT analysis; Aydın and Aydın (2015), on the other hand, evaluated Turkey's health tourism practices in national and international markets comparatively. These studies reveal the advantages and disadvantages of Turkey in the context of marketing strategies. Erkiılıç and Eren (2020), on the other hand, found that elderly and disabled individuals could not benefit from the tour services offered by travel agencies; It has been revealed that this group is not considered as an alternative market by most agencies. On the other hand, Özçelik et al. (2021) analyzed the general functioning process of health tourism activities from the perspective of travel agencies and revealed the positions of these actors in the sector more clearly. These studies show that health tourism travel agencies play important roles not only as service providers, but also in terms of strategic planning and customer guidance. The study of Dalkıran and Bayrak (2020) aimed to examine the functionality and content quality of the websites of intermediary institutions in health tourism. It has been concluded that in regions where health tourism activities are intense, the number of businesses is high and these organizations use health tourism marketing-oriented visuals.

The aim of this study is to reveal the role and importance of health tourism travel agencies in the development of health tourism. In this context, the sub-objectives of the research are as follows;

1. What is the role of health tourism travel agencies in the development of health tourism?
2. What is the contribution of health tourism travel agencies in the development of health tourism?
3. What is the effect of health tourism travel agencies on patient satisfaction in the development of health tourism?

2. METHOD

2.1. Model of the Research

In the study, a mixed method based on both quantitative and qualitative data was used as a model. Mixed research method means that both quantitative and qualitative research methods are used together in research. This method is used to answer research questions more comprehensively and to gain a deeper understanding of research results. Mixed research involves two or more different research methods to both collect and analyze quantitative data (numerical data) and qualitative data (written or oral data such as open-ended questions, interviews, focus groups) (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008). The qualitative dimension of the

research consisted of the relevant literature review and the quantitative dimension consisted of the data collected with the help of a questionnaire.

2.2. Scope and Limitations

According to the 2023 data of the General Directorate of Health Services, it has been determined that a total of 621 intermediary facilities in Turkey have authorization certificates. The universe of the study includes agencies active in the health tourism sector throughout Turkey. The sample of the research is 5 agencies determined by purposive sampling. In total, the study was carried out with 25 participants working in the agency. They were preferred according to the maximum diversity criterion. In the collection of qualitative data, researches on the subject in the literature will be examined. On 15.04.2025, the words “health tourism” and “agency” were scanned in the abstract to the keywords made from the YÖK thesis. The information of the agency officers is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Information of Agency Officers

		<i>f</i>	%
Gender	Woman	5	20
	Male	20	80
	Sum	25	100,0
Age Range	18-29	5	20
	30-44	15	60
	45 years and older	5	20
	Sum	25	100,0
Education Level	High school	2	8,0
	Associate Degree	8	32,0
	License	10	40,0
	Graduate	5	20,0
	Sum	25	100,0
Experience	0-1 year	2	8,0
	2-5 years	8	32,0
	6-10 years	5	20,0
	11 years and above	10	40,0
	Sum	25	100,0

In Table 1, information about agency officers is given. According to the gender distribution, 80% of the participants are male and 20% are female. When analyzed by age range, 20% are between the ages of 18-29, 60% are between the ages of 30-44, and 20% are between the ages of 45 and over. Considering the level of education, 40% of the participants have a bachelor's degree, 32% have an associate degree, 20% have a graduate degree, and 8% have a high school degree. According to the length of experience, 40% have 11 years or more of experience, while 32% have 2-5 years, 20% have 6-10 years and 8% have 0-1 years of experience.

2.3. Data Collection Technique and Analysis

In the study, a questionnaire form was used for quantitative data and a literature review was used for qualitative data. Relevant companies were contacted and data were collected by face-to-face interviews. The Health tourism agencies satisfaction survey prepared by Berksoy (2022) was used as a data collection tool. The questionnaire is a Likert-type scale

consisting of 5 demographic information and 24 closed-ended questions. Content analysis and frequency analysis methods were used in the analysis of the data (Gedik and Mengü, 2019).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Quantitative Findings

The findings of the data obtained through the health tourism agencies satisfaction survey are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Tourism Agencies Satisfaction Mean and Standard Deviations

	Average	Standard deviation
1. There are problems that prevent the activities of health tourism travel agencies.	4,20	2,16
2. The waiting times for the treatment of health tourists who come through health tourism agencies are shorter than those who come by different means.	3,24	2,14
3. Health tourism agencies provide lower-cost treatments to health tourists.	3,15	2,11
4. Health tourism agencies offer more reliable and comfortable treatments to health tourists.	3,38	2,05
5. Health tourism agencies continue to take care of the patient after the end of the treatment of health tourists.	3,17	2,08
6. Health tourism agencies provide services for the special needs of health tourists before and after their treatment.	3,80	2,19
7. Health tourism businesses provide health tourists with the opportunity to take a holiday before or after treatment.	3,82	2,27
8. Confidentiality regarding the operation of patients coming through health tourism agencies is important.	3,93	2,09
9. Within the scope of the services provided by health tourism agencies, the most important feature that should be present in the personnel should be foreign language.	5,11	2,07
10. The participation of health tourism agencies in domestic and international fairs has an important role in the development of health tourism.	3,80	2,22
11. Health tourism agencies make enough advertising and promotion.	4,28	2,15
12. Advertising and promotional activities of health tourism agencies contribute greatly to the development of health tourism.	3,30	2,05
13. Health tourism agencies have significant contributions to international competition.	3,54	2,24
14. Health tourism agencies contribute to the cultural and social development of our country.	3,18	2,07
15. The current situation of our country in the field of health tourism is at a satisfactory level.	3,75	2,26
16. Health tourists coming to Turkey mostly prefer medical tourism.	3,92	2,15
17. Health tourists coming to Turkey mostly prefer thermal tourism.	4,30	2,06
18. Health tourists coming to Turkey mostly prefer elderly and disabled tourism.	3,93	2,16
19. The geographical location of our country is advantageous enough in the selection of health tourism.	2,71	1,87
20. Tourists who come to our country for health tourism financially satisfy health tourism travel agencies.	3,39	2,07
21. Health tourism is one of the important sources of income in our country.	4,39	2,10
22. Due to the pandemic that started in 2020 in the world and in our country, health tourism has been adversely affected.	3,52	2,17
23. The facilities for health tourism in our country meet the potential.	3,25	2,05
24. As a health tourism travel agency, I am hopeful for the future of this tourism.	3,87	2,20

Looking at Table 2; The highest satisfaction of the participants was given to the statements “The most important feature that should be present in the personnel within the scope of the services provided by health tourism agencies should be foreign language” (Average: 5.11) and “Health tourism is one of the important sources of income of our

country” (Average: 4.39). On the other hand, the statement “The geographical location of our country is advantageous enough in the selection of health tourism” (Average: 2.71) indicates a lower level of satisfaction.

3.2. Qualitative Findings

3.2.1. Theme and Sub-Themes

Theme 1: The Effects of the Internet on Health Tourism Travel Agencies

Subtheme 1.1: Internet Adoption and Marketing Strategies

The research of Abou-Shouk, Lim and Megicks (2013) reveals the view that the adoption of the internet by health tourism travel agencies can provide the most effective marketing tool and competitive advantage for their businesses. It has been stated that travel agencies use the internet to provide customer information, conduct competitor analysis and improve their marketing activities.

Sub-Theme 1.2: Obstacles to the Use of the Internet

According to research, factors such as limited resources, unskilled workforce, lack of readiness of public infrastructure, and customers' lack of adoption of internet technologies stand out as the main obstacles limiting the development of health tourism travel agencies' websites.

Theme 2: Content Analysis and Impact of Health Tourism Travel Agencies' Websites

Sub-Theme 2.1: Deficiencies in Medical Tourism Agencies' Websites and Risk Communication

The study of Penney, Snyder, Crooks, and Johnston (2011) reveals that the websites of medical tourism agencies in Canada contain deficiencies and are inadequate in terms of risk communication. It has been emphasized that this situation may expose medical tourists to incomplete or misleading information and raise ethical concerns.

Sub-Theme 2.2: General Website Effectiveness and Marketing Strategies in Tourism

In our country, researches showing that the websites of organizations in the tourism sector are not used effectively enough (Doğan and Kekeç Morkoç, 2015) draw attention. It has been concluded that websites are not considered as an effective factor in sales and marketing, and there are deficiencies in the content especially for domestic tourism.

Sub-Theme 2.3: Content Analysis of Health Tourism and Thermal Hotels' Websites

Ceylan's (2018) study shows that the content of the websites of thermal hotels is insufficient and there is a need for more information to be provided to tourists. It has been emphasized that more effective and efficient use of websites can enable the development of hotels providing thermal services and provide better service.

These themes and sub-themes constitute an important framework to understand the role of health tourism travel agencies and the contributions of the effective use of websites to the development of health tourism.

4. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study is based on a survey conducted to evaluate the role and importance of health tourism travel agencies. The findings show that health tourism travel agencies contribute to customer satisfaction in a number of factors. In addition, qualitative data

provides a detailed overview of topics such as the functions of travel agencies, information communication technologies and health tourism authorization certificates.

Participants generally have a positive outlook on the services offered by health tourism travel agencies. “The most important feature that should be present in the personnel should be a foreign language” and “Health tourism is an important source of income for our country” have the highest satisfaction levels. This situation shows that health tourism travel agencies focus on the quality of personnel and the contribution of the sector to the country's economy in order to increase customer satisfaction.

The main functions of travel agencies are explained as meeting touristic needs and ensuring their relocation. In addition, travel agencies have duties such as marketing the products of tour operators, taking reservations, providing local transportation and providing information to holiday buyers. This shows that health tourism travel agencies focus on the role of coordinating tourist activities and providing support to health tourists. Information and communication technologies emphasize that travel agencies are a critical factor in determining the competitiveness of today. Internet and information technologies provide health tourism travel agencies with the opportunity to provide customer information, develop marketing strategies and gain competitive advantage. However, factors such as limited resources and customers' lack of adoption of internet technologies may limit the adoption of these technologies. The health tourism authorization certificate shows that health tourism travel agencies in Turkey must meet certain standards. There are various criteria to have an international health tourism authorization certificate. These criteria aim to ensure that health tourism travel agencies meet certain standards and provide international health tourism services.

Theme 1 examines the effects of the internet on health tourism travel agencies. Subtheme 1.1 discusses internet adoption and marketing strategies. This highlights the importance of travel agencies using the internet as an effective marketing tool. Subtheme 1.2 focuses on the obstacles encountered in the use of the internet and shows that factors such as limited resources, unskilled labor can limit the development of travel agencies' websites. Theme 2 deals with the content analysis and effects of the websites of health tourism travel agencies. Sub-theme 2.1 highlights the deficiencies in the websites of medical tourism agencies and the inadequacies in risk communication. Sub-theme 2.2 evaluates overall website effectiveness and marketing strategies in tourism. Sub-theme 2.3 deals with the content analysis of the websites of health tourism and thermal hotels.

This study evaluates the effects of health tourism travel agencies on customer satisfaction, their functions, the use of information and communication technologies and the requirements for authorization certificates. The findings show that travel agencies generally contribute to a positive customer satisfaction. It also provides an important framework for understanding the effects of factors such as internet adoption, content analysis of websites, and health tourism authorization documents on the development of health tourism. At this point, it is important that health tourism travel agencies should use information and communication technologies more effectively in order to provide more effective services and increase their competitive advantage in the sector.

The findings show that the participants generally have a positive perspective on the services offered by health tourism travel agencies. In particular, high satisfaction rates were reported to the statements “The most important feature that should be present in the personnel should be a foreign language” and “Health tourism is an important source of income for our country”. Based on these positive findings, health tourism travel agencies can further improve the foreign language skills of the staff and further increase their contribution to the country's

economy in order to increase customer satisfaction and improve service quality. However, the statement “The geographical location of our country is advantageous enough in the selection of health tourism” indicates a lower level of satisfaction. At this point, more effective marketing of geographical advantages and creating more awareness of the potential of health tourism may allow tourists to take better advantage of these advantages in choosing a country.

As emphasized in the study, information and communication technologies are a critical factor that provides competitive advantage for health tourism travel agencies. However, obstacles such as limited resources and customer failure to adopt internet technologies can be encountered. In this context, travel agencies should adopt a more effective digital marketing strategy and better communicate the advantages of using the internet to customers. At the same time, more investment in staff training may be required to improve digital skills in the sector.

The obligation of international health tourism authorization documents to meet certain standards can help travel agencies to ensure quality in health tourism services. However, meeting certain criteria can sometimes be challenging. Health tourism travel agencies can cooperate and make necessary improvements to better comply with these standards and obtain authorization certificates.

The themes and sub-themes addressed in the study offer the potential for further research and analysis. In particular, the impact of the internet on the marketing strategies of health tourism travel agencies and the content analysis of websites may require a more detailed examination. In this context, it may be recommended that these issues be addressed in more detail in future research. The results of this study highlight the potential of health tourism travel agencies and their contribution to customer satisfaction, while at the same time showing opportunities for development in certain areas. In order to increase customer satisfaction and maintain a competitive advantage in the sector, travel agencies should use information and communication technologies more effectively, better market their geographical advantages and comply more with international standards. By focusing on these recommendations in future research, it can contribute to the sustainable development of health tourism.

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